

A Study on the Emerging Trends in Stress Management of College Teachers

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Introduction :

“Teacher is a maker of man. He is foundation of all Education, and thus of the whole civilization of mankind, present and future. No nation reconstruction is possible without the active cooperation of the teacher.”

 John Adams

Teaching is one of the most significant and visible profession in the world. Teacher is a representative of the society who inculcates moral precepts. In the development of a country, great attention has to be paid to education and learning, as well as good morals, and nobody is more suited to assist in this process than the humble teacher. Without teachers, both knowledge and morals would suffer. Colleges are as important institutions as any other organization of the society. Teaching has ever been accorded autonomy of full professional status. It has an appropriate responsibility in fostering the development of youths. It is very important due to its

responsibility because child development and well being are taken as central concerns. Women college teachers tried their best to perform their duties at job and home as well. They tried to fulfill expectations of family members and at the same time they are expected to be active member at Colleges.

Main sources of College teachers stress :

- Excessive workload and working hours often exacerbated by a surfeit of government 'initiatives'
- Poor pupil behaviour, which itself is often compounded by issues such as large class size
- Pressures of assessment targets and inspections
- Management bullying; and
- Lack of professional opportunities.

Stress Relief Tips for College teachers :

Expectations from college teachers are huge, what with they being responsible for students futures. With so many burdens on their shoulders, college teachers might sometimes feel tense and carry this tension with them to their classes. So, stress management for college teachers becomes mandatory. Here are a few proven stress relief tips for college teachers which are sure to eliminate stress from their lives.

1. Keep Calm :

If you feel really angry or upset in class give yourself time to feel it later on when you are alone or away from the children. Releasing when you are alone is fine it's just not such a good idea in class as this will just create more stress.

2. Practice Stress Relief Regularly :

If you don't practice meditation then please go here to learn. Meditation is a wonderful way of dealing with stress. Not only does it give you perspective but it also calms and relaxes you. Get into a routine of practicing stress management.

3. Be Centered Before Going into Class :

If you don't feel good, or upset and angry then the students will pick up on it. They know because they are really sensitive. This will potentially make your day difficult if they decide to prod you. Before going into class spend a few minutes centering our self :

- Focus your attention 2 fingers' breadth below the belly button.
- Breathe in 4 short intakes of air to that point. Keep your focus there.
- Hold your breath and tense your stomach muscles 4 times.
- Breathe out 4 short breaths while keeping your focus there.
- Do this for a few minutes and you should feel much centered.

4. Compassion :

Another good stress management for teacher's technique is to be compassionate. Have compassion for the children. They might be going through a hard time at home or with friends and a lot of children are not good at expressing this. Rather than speak about it, they let it build and place this emotion onto others.

5. Laugh with the Class :

Have you ever fallen over or done something stupid in class? Has the class burst out in laughter? Did you laugh with them? If this does happen again go with the flow and laugh.

6. Connect with nature :

Spending time outside in nature is good for the body and the mind. It helps relieve feelings of worry, anxiety and stress. Natural beauty distracts us from problems and just helps us feel good. Studies show that being in nature or even viewing scenes of nature, reduce anger, fear, and stress and increases pleasant feelings. Exposure to nature not only makes you feel better emotionally, but it also contributes to your physical wellbeing, reducing blood pressure, heart rate, muscle tension, and the production of stress hormones.

7. Listen to soothing music :

The soothing power of music is well-established. It affects our emotions and can be an extremely effective stress management tool.

Soothing music can slow the pulse and heart rate, lower blood pressure and decrease the levels of stress hormones, and distract us from our worries. Research shows that listening to music can help a person with clinical depression or bipolar disorder get through their worst, lowest moods.

8. Practicing Yoga & Reiki :

The ultimate goal of Yoga is stilling the mind and gaining insight, resting in detached awareness, released moksha from Samsara and dukkha. A process or discipline leading to oneness with the divine or with one's self. The formulation of this goal varies with the philosophical or theological system with which it is conjugated. In the classical astanga yoga system, the ultimate goal of yoga practice is to achieve the state of samadhi and abide in that state as pure awareness. Reiki increases the body's natural abilities through transfer of energy from a Reiki practitioner to the affected person. Both yoga and reiki provide stress relief.

Massage Therapy :

Massage therapy provides relaxation to the body. Massages rejuvenate the body by improving the blood circulation. Pamper yourself by getting a message from a professional. Alternatively, take a bubble bath at home. Draw a bath with lukewarm water. Add bath salts and aromatherapy oils to it. Keep scented candles all around and your relaxing bath will be ready.

Making Time for Yourself :

Manage your time well by proper planning and prioritizing your work. This way you will be able to keep some time solely for yourself. Take care of your diet by including lots of vegetables and fresh fruits. Sleep for at least 7-8 hours at night. Change your appearance a bit. Get a new haircut, manicure or pedicure. Once in a while, do things only for yourself.

Conclusion :

College teachers are essential for the effective functioning of education system and for improving the quality of learning processes. College teachers play an important role in constructing the personality of their students. College teachers are very important and valuable to our society. Hence, stress management for college teachers is of utmost importance. Here's hoping that these stress relief tips for college teachers will replenish them physically, mentally and emotionally.

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